

Data Model to Digitization of Criticality Analysis in Railway Systems

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Abstract

This article introduces an innovative perspective for criticality analysis in railway systems by incorporating digitization as an enabler for automated and on-demand assessment of the risk value for each asset. In contrast to previous static approaches, our method leverages digitization to enable dynamic analysis of the criticality of railway components, enhancing decision-making in maintenance management. The proposed approach follows a detailed data Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) process, starting with comprehensive data collection, including maintenance records, asset attributes, and classification. This facilitates the integration of diverse non-standardized data sources, allowing for a digital representation of assets. By characterizing assets through attributes, a quantitative evaluation of criticality is achieved, improving efficiency through an automated process. This characterization not only streamlines the assessment but also enables the application of the model in scenarios of high complexity, volume, and operational variability, such as railway infrastructures with millions of assets. The precise assessment of criticality adapts to changing railway conditions, enabling the organization to identify patterns and generate risk alerts. Criticality scores are integrated with the enterprise asset management system, triggering specific actions in response to significant risk variations. The results demonstrate significant improvements in maintenance resource allocation, including a reduction in interventions for low-criticality assets. Additionally, it enables root cause analysis for high-risk assets, resulting in cost reduction, downtime reduction, and improvement in safety. The data normalization approach through submodels allows adaptation to various railway contexts, providing a comprehensive solution for criticality analysis and other analyses. The applied case study focuses on a section of a metropolitan commuter rail network with over 700,000 assets, illustrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach in practice. Simultaneously, these results have been utilized in applications and research to forecast risks in railway infrastructures, solidifying the value and applicability of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Criticality Analysis; Data model; Digitization; Railway Maintenance Management

1. Introduction

Understanding asset criticality is crucial for the safety of railway infrastructure. This study aims to integrate digital tools into criticality analysis, prioritizing agile and efficient decision-making to allocate resources effectively and achieve significant cost savings. The main objective is to present an innovative data model that enables dynamic integration and efficient utilization of information, surpassing traditional static approaches. The pioneering approach of Asset Attributes Characterization (AAC) is introduced, allowing the digital representation of the asset and applied submodels to provide values and states essential for any required analysis (Cavalieri & Salafia, 2020). The research focuses on the application of digital tools in railway maintenance management, emphasizing the analysis of equipment failures and their impact on transportation (Ram & Tyagi, 2021). An integrated technique is proposed, involving the grouping and characterization of devices, performance evaluation through fault record analysis, and association of multiple information sources through normalized relationships. This facilitates the assignment of comparable values to each attribute, defining primary elements (intervention level), and linking them to secondary elements contributing to the system's performance. In summary, the study

aims to enhance data utilization and integration for efficient evaluation and prioritization of assets, ensuring focused decision-making. The research questions guiding this work are: How to use an ETL model to normalize data? In what ways does the AAC Data Model contribute to criticality assessment? How does the generation of digital assets through characterization enable criticality analysis? These questions will be addressed throughout the document and via a case study, providing a valuable contribution to the digital transformation of criticality analysis in railway networks, with direct impact on maintenance engineering practices in the sector.

2. Literature review

Research on the integration of data for dynamic criticality analysis in railway infrastructure is advancing, yet confined to localized contexts. (McMahon et al., 2020) compile scientific sources on Big Data analysis, including railway asset management, but fall short of exploring dynamic criticality analysis. Our study aims to bridge these gaps. (Roda et al., 2023) focus on leveraging Big Data for strategic asset management but lack integration of non-standard data with digital transformation for dynamic criticality analysis in railroads. Similarly, (Magnien et al., 2022) standardize railway traffic management data needs but require digital transformation for dynamic criticality analysis in ensuring safety. (MacChi et al., 2012) provide a robust base model for railway system maintenance but advocate for a family of items approach. (Ghofrani et al., 2018) emphasize Big Data analytics for optimizing railway transportation but call for digital transformation in dynamic, data-driven criticality analysis. (Figueres-Esteban et al., 2015) focus on improving train safety with Visual Analytics, emphasizing ETL procedures and digital transformation for dynamic decision-making in maintenance. (Attoh-Okine, 2014) highlights Big Data benefits for railway safety, yet advocates for digital transformation in criticality analysis. In simpler terms, prior studies often overlook Asset Attributes Characterization (AAC) for practical integration of multiple sources, relying on data from specific applications. In contrast, our research incorporates AAC for comprehensive asset tracking, enhancing maintenance decision-making. This marks a significant evolution from the conventional, static approach. In summary, our research addresses gaps by: (i) conducting dynamic criticality analysis using a data-driven approach; (ii) employing enhanced data analysis for accurate predictive maintenance; (iii) structuring data for digital asset creation, setting the precedent for their digital twins. This review highlights three key aspects: (i) Criticality models in the railway context, (ii) Data models driving management models in railways, and (iii) Big Data challenges: heterogeneity, volume, and sources.

3. Methodology

This research aims to present a process for structuring a data model that facilitates the digitization of criticality analysis, consequently enhancing decision-making in maintenance management. Current methods for criticality analysis in railway engineering rely on static information and expert judgment, which, while effective due to their simplicity, become complex when applied to massive asset contexts with diverse operational settings. The demand for automation that allows on-demand pre-evaluation, validated by specialists or directly consumed by the decision-making process, is evident. The project addresses these limitations through the development of a model for analysis, extraction, relationship, integration, and normalization of data. This is applied to a numerical criticality evaluation methodology based on attribute assessment for each asset class in its specific operational context. The study introduces a data model that transforms information from various sources (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Data process for the Criticality Analysis

through relationships and queries, enabling the creation of the master database. This database executes the model's business rules, resulting in criticality evaluation, visually presented in a matrix segmented by ranges determining the associated levels of criticality for each set of assets. Subsequently, algorithms (sets of rules) analyze attribute values, calculating the impact based on potential operational system contexts and predefined criteria in each case. The process involves attribute and asset characterization, data collection, and normalization, rule application for different asset types, and the creation of models or rule sets, culminating in assigning a numerical value to each asset for positioning in a criticality ranking. To aid understanding, a diagram illustrating the problem-solving process is suggested (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Visual representation of the data flows and business rules

This visual representation illustrates data flows from identifying operational entities existing in heterogeneous information sources, normalized through relationship tables, yielding another subset of data. This subset then provides each asset with a value for each attribute, based on the asset type, operational context, and defined intervention level. Once each asset possesses its set

of attributes from these sub-models, performance data such as failure frequency, unavailability, delayed trains, canceled trains, etc., are related to each asset, adding a technical location criterion, defined by functional paths or UFS (Rodríguez et al., 2023). These are categorized as linear or discrete and represent the traveled section from point A to point B, defined in this case as a station. After characterizing assets with both on-demand operational data and operational performance data, the information is centralized in the Master database. Business rules defined according to the company's thresholds are applied to automatically evaluate the individual value of each asset. As a future research point, it is highlighted that building the master data set could be enriched with other attributes, for example, real-time health status measurement, after applying its respective model. Similarly, performance data can be modeled using machine learning algorithms, enabling risk value prediction and potentially anticipating strategies. The significance of criticality analysis lies in providing a holistic view of assets based on their impact on general functions and the probability of failure. The difficulty of measuring this impact and capturing operational performance data necessitates input normalization, where digitization plays a crucial role in creating digital assets that replicate the physical asset through a set of attributes. This implies transforming various data sets into a common format for a standardized analysis.

4. Case study

The case study revolves around a metropolitan commuter rail network with approximately 700,000 assets. One of the busiest lines was selected for evaluation, encompassing over 12,000 elements initially, later narrowed down to around 4,000 "evaluatable assets" based on their intervention levels. The remaining inventory is linked as parent-child structures to these evaluatable assets, contributing data to assess the parent's performance. The second extraction package focuses on asset performance, pulling records of faults from the last six years, totaling over 200,000 events. These are then segmented and filtered to about 13,000 records relevant to the study. Notably, the fault descriptions are still conducted through open text, limiting in-depth analysis of the failure mode. However, criteria are established to derive values at the element level within a section. Exclusion of maintenance cost allocation aspects from the ERP analysis is attributed to the current insufficient data quality. Following the initial extraction and cleansing, multiple attributes such as track speed, circulation frequency, affected environmental zones, tunnels, bridges, and curves are obtained from diverse heterogeneous sources. These data necessitate normalization for proper association with assets. In the transformation phase, the initial inventory data is utilized to generate digital assets with associated attributes. Through business rules (See Fig 3), these are individually evaluated to assign a criticality value based on the probability of failure and impact.

Figure 3 – Example of a rules for a severity factor (Safety)

Once loaded into the master database, they are consumed by the specific criticality model defined by rules concerning asset type, impact dimension, and attribute. Ultimately, they are visually presented through a control panel (Fig. 5), providing an overview of all asset statuses. These scores can automatically trigger maintenance processes and alerts upon surpassing predefined thresholds in the Enterprise Asset Management (EAM) system. The data model for this digitized

criticality analysis represents a significant advancement by offering a dynamic, data-driven, and quantitative approach.

Figure 5 – Example of the resulted Criticality Matrix

5. Result analysis and discussion

The integration of criticality analysis into railway systems through digitization is revolutionizing railway maintenance management. This model showcases outstanding proficiency in dynamically assessing criticality by leveraging on-demand data. Incorporating asset attribute characterization enables on-demand representation of asset conditions, fostering precise and adaptable quantitative criticality calculation. In a practical application on a commuter rail line, the digital criticality analysis model allowed for the semi-automatic evaluation of thousands of assets. It successfully defined rules and data structures scalable to the entire network, with the caveat of requiring review upon the inclusion of new asset types and attributes not present in the case study. The significant advancement lies in the model's adaptability, exhaustive criticality analysis, and versatility achieved through data normalization and submodels (Crespo Márquez, 2022). The integration of criticality scores into the Enterprise Asset Management (EAM) system will simplify decision-making for railway infrastructure. Future research aims to refine validation rules for multiple information sources within specific railway operators, consider new operational conditions, explore possibilities offered by digital tools for performance prediction, and ultimately create standardized submodels of digital assets characterizing each physical asset. This establishes a digital DNA with attributes and data that can be queried and associated with any business management model without forceful relationships.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study introduces an innovative digital transformation in railway criticality analysis, enhancing safety and reliability. Utilizing a dynamic approach and ETL process, comprehensive data is collected for assessing the criticality of railway components. Asset characterization through attributes enables a digital representation and automated quantitative calculations, enhancing assessment efficiency. The integration of criticality scores with enterprise asset management systems enables faster and more precise decision-making. In a practical case, the model demonstrated improvements in resource allocation and downtime prediction, anticipating critical assets. While the model is scalable, future challenges, such as refining validation rules and exploring machine learning tools, are identified. This approach significantly contributes to the digital transformation in railway networks, serving as a valuable reference for future research in railway maintenance management. In conclusion, digitization provides a

comprehensive solution to enhance criticality analysis, emphasizing its adaptability and effectiveness in managing large volumes of railway assets.

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3rd OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 10.00	WELCOME - OPENING ADRESSES			
10.00 10.45	PLENARY SESSION ISABEL PARDO DE VERA. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE: PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO			
10.45 11.15	COFFEE BREAK			
11.15 12.45	RAIL SESSION Digitalization in manufacturing and O&M of railway rolling stock	CIBERSECURITY SESSION Decentralized cybersecurity of critical engineering assets	Strategy & Planning	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 1
12.45 14.15	LUNCH			
14.15 15.00	PLENARY SESSION CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH, COPPERLEAF. OPTIMISED ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING WITH COPPERLEAF - MAKING THE RIGHT DECISIONS AT THE RIGHT TIME TO MAXIMISE VALUE AND MEET STRATEGIC GOALS			
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17.00 18.30	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	HYDROGEN SESSION Technical and Energetic Challenges in the Transition from Natural gas to Hydrogen	Life Cycle Management 2	SPECIAL SESSION Digital IAMS for integral LCM
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL			

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09.45 10.30	PLENARY SESSION NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUAEPAL.			
10.30 11.00	COFFEE BREAK			
11.00 12.30	APMI-AEM SESSION Maintenance and Asset Management. Future and Trends in the Iberian Region	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION BIOCHAR Applications and Circular Economy	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 1	WORKSHOP The Copperleaf optimization game
12.30 14.00	LUNCH			
14.00 14.45	PLENARY SESSION. TIAGO FERNANDES, ALFONSO LACERDA. EVORA GOLD PARTNER SAP. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE- THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL WORLD.			
14.45 16.15	APMI-AEM SESSION People in Maintenance and Asset management in the Iberian Region	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Improving asset management in local governments	Management Systems and Standards 1	Sustainability 1
16.15 16.45	COFFEE BREAK			
16.45 18.15	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Building sustainable communities with asset management	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 2	Management Systems and Standards 2
20.00	GALA DINNER			

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09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION. JOE AMADI-ECHENDU , DAVID MCKEON,, EDMEA ADELL, ALAN WILSON. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS .			
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11.45 13.15	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION Intelligent Asset Management : People, Processes and Technology as enablers for ISO 55001 Certification	Data Asset and Digital Transformation	Sustainability 3	People & Competence
13.15 14.00	CLOSING CEREMONY			
14.00	LUNCH			

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10.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 44. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO. ISABEL PARDO DE VERA.
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11.15 AUDITORIUM III	CYBERSECURITY SESSION. ID 58. NAORIS PROTOCOL: WORLD'S FIRST DECENTRALIZED CYBERSECURITY MESH ARCHITECTURE. DAVID CARVALHO
	ID 116. BRIDGING THE GAP: WEB 3.0 AND CYBER-PHYSICAL INTEGRATION IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT
	<i>Chair: João Santos. Naoris David Carvalho. Naoris Miguel Oliveira. University of Aveiro Luis Ramalhão Santos. OET Jorge Liça. OE Carlos Ribeiro. Ex Director CSI</i>
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ID 21	EXPLORING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT'S EFFECT ON LIFE CYCLE COSTS WITH DIGITALIZATION'S SUPPORT. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ-PRIDA
ID 24	EARLY FAILURE DETECTION IN SECONDARY CRYOGENIC PUMPS THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY 4.0. SONIA LIÑAN
ID 45	DYNAMIC FLEET MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT: INTEGRATING PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE AND PREDICTIVE CBM WITH OPERATION SCHEDULING. ADOLFO CRESPO DEL CASTILLO
ID 46	FRAMEWORK FOR ASSET DIGITALIZATION: A HOLISTIC APPROACH FOR ENHANCED MANAGEMENT AND RELIABILITY IN THE DIGITAL ERA. EDUARDO CANDÓN
ID 47	STRATEGIC INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE: TRANSFORMING ASSET MANAGEMENT ACROSS THE LIFECYCLE FOR INFORMED DECISION-MAKING. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
ID 80	DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT. GFM&AM'S PROJECT 25DX INSIGHTS. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL OCEANÁRIO

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09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 123. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE INFRAESTRUCTURAS. ABEL GOMES. APPLUS.
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 134. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUA. NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL.
10.30	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY AYESA
11.00 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 121 MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT: FUTURE AND TRENDS IN THE IBERO-AMERICAN SPACE <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez Claudio Rodríguez. AEM Diogo Brito. APMI Marcela Scalco. ABRAMAN</i>
	ID 122. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Pedro Conceição (SONAE ARAUCO) Hugo Lebre (INFRASPEAK) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM III	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION. ID 95: BIOCHAR APPLICATIONS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY. ATIV <i>Chair: Cátia Neves. ATIV - Mota ENGIL</i>
11.00 ROOM 2	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 1. ANTONIO GUILLÉN LÓPEZ.
ID 11	THE IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE ASSET MAINTENANCE IN TELECOMS DOMAIN IN EMERGING MARKETS. CHARLES OKEYIA
ID 13	CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY AND OVERCOMING THE DIGITALIZATION DEFICIT OF THE AECO INDUSTRY. SEYED REZVAN
ID 89	IMPLANTAÇÃO DE SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA EMBASA: INTEGRAÇÃO DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO. RINALDO CAMURUGY
ID 33	MODELAÇÃO PARAMÉTRICA DE ANOMALIAS EM TÚNEIS FERROVIÁRIOS. ANA ROCHA
ID 106	A VALUE-BASED DECISION-MAKING PROCESS FOR DIGITAL TWINNING OPPORTUNITIES IN RAIL AND ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET MANAGEMENT. JOÃO VIEIRA

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ID 3	DIGITALIZATION STRATEGY FOR ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY'S NET-ZERO TRANSITION. <i>ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM II	WORKSHOP. ID 5. THE COPPERLEAF OPTIMIZATION GAME. CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH.
12.30	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
14.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 130. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE – THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN A DIGITAL WORLD. TIAGO FERNANDES, SAP & ALFONSO LACERDA, EVORA.
14.45 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 124. PEOPLE IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION .
	<i>Chair: Daniel Gaspar José Luis Bernal. MASA Álvaro Rodríguez Prieto. UNED Paulo Peixoto (ATEC) Mário Aguiam (ISQ)</i>
14.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 96. IMPROVING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
14.45 ROOM 2	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 1. CHAIR RITA BRITO.
ID 19	SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA MANUTENÇÃO DE PAVIMENTOS RODOVIÁRIOS. <i>JOSÉ VAZ</i>
ID 27	LOS SISTEMAS DE GETIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE CARRETERAS COMO HERRAMIENTAS PARA LA OPTIMIZACIÓN DE LOS PRESUPUESTOS DE CONSERVACIÓN. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 83	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS APLICADA EMPRESAS DE SANEAMENTO: IMPLANTAÇÃO DE MODELO NA EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO (EMBASA). <i>ALISSON BRANDÃO</i>
ID 77	NEW VALUE PERSPECTIVE FOR SOCIAL PRICELESS ASSETS THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS. <i>JOAQUÍN ORDIERES-MERÉ</i>
ID 78	DESAFIOS ATUAIS DA E-REDES NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS TÉCNICOS. <i>MIGUEL FREITAS</i>
14.45 ROOM 5	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 1. CHAIR: ANA SILVA.
ID 56	AVALIAÇÃO EX-ANTE DA PRODUÇÃO DE MISTURAS BETUMINOSAS CONSIDERANDO TRÊS CENÁRIOS DE PRODUÇÃO ALTERNATIVOS. <i>ANA ROCHA</i>

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ID 71	THE SYNERGY BETWEEN LEAN PHILOSOPHY AND VALUE ENGINEERING FOR NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 72	SOLUÇÃO CONJUGADA DE CONSTRUÇÃO TRADICIONAL E TECNOLOGIA MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS SUSTENTÁVEIS EM CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTES</i>
ID 75	"BOTICAR" PROJECT – THE FIRST STEPS TOWARDS DECARBONISATION IN PORTUGAL
ID 90	IMPLANTAÇÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NO SISTEMA DE ABASTECIMENTO DE ÁGUA E ESGOTAMENTO SANITÁRIO DE BARRA DE POJUCA NA EMBASA – EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO. <i>RINALDO CAMURUGY</i>
16.15	COFFEE BREAK
16.45 AUDITORIUM I	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR JOAQUÍN ORDIERES
	GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. TALGO
ID 128	IMPORTANCIA DEL FACTOR HUMANO EN LA APLICACIÓN DE LA INGENIERÍA DEL MANTENIMIENTO EN LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS. <i>JOSÉ LUIS BERNAL. MASA</i>
ID 115	UN ENFOQUE UNIFICADO DE LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS MEDIANTE SAP Y BIM EN AT/MT/BT ELÉCTRICA. <i>IGNACIO MORATALLA AGUIRRE. AYESA</i>
16.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 97. BUILDING SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITIES WITH ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
16.45 ROOM 2	DATA ASSETS & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 2. CHAIR: VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA.
ID 15	INDUSTRIAL IOT AND 3D DIGITAL TWIN FOR REAL TIME-EVERGREENING OF ENGINEERING ASSETS SUBJECTED TO CORROSION UNDER INSULATION. <i>ALVARO RODRÍGUEZ-PRIETO</i>
ID 26	UNA EFICAZ GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE REDES DE CARRETERAS A PARTIR DE GEMELOS DIGITALES. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 70	OVERVIEW OF THE USE OF DATA ASSETS IN THE CONTEXT OF PORTUGUESE COMPANIES: COMPARISON BETWEEN SMES AND LARGE COMPANIES. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 73	MODIFICAÇÃO DO MÉTODO DELPHI PARA APLICAÇÃO NUM QUESTIONÁRIO SOBRE A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>SAMUEL MESSIAS</i>
ID 103	NDE & SENSING SOLUTIONS FOR PIPELINE STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING. <i>GABRIEL DINIS</i>
ID 112	DIGITALIZING BUILDING MAINTENANCE: BIM-POWERED ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS. <i>ANA SILVA</i>

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16.45 ROOM 5	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 2. FILIPA SALVADO.
ID 16	COLLECTIVE USE BUILDINGS ASSET MANAGEMENT BASED ON TECHNICAL AND ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO</i>
ID 35	IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS OF AN ISO 55001 CERTIFIED ASSET MANAGEMENT MODEL IN THE NATURAL GAS INDUSTRY. <i>JAVIER SERRA</i>
ID 41	IMPLEMENTACIÓN DE UN PLAN DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS SEGÚN LA NORMA ISO 55001 EN LA CENTRAL DE GENERACIÓN ELÉCTRICA COLMITO.
ID 63	A EVOLUÇÃO E PERSPETIVAS DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS: UM MODELO ABRANGENTE E INTEGRADO DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS. <i>JOAQUIM CABRAL MARTINS</i>
ID 82	CERTIFICAÇÃO ISO 55001 NA E-REDES – UMA AVALIAÇÃO APÓS DOIS ANOS. <i>CRISTINA CARVALHO</i>
ID 110	IMPORTÂNCIA DO ALINHAMENTO DAS FUNÇÕES ORGANIZACIONAIS E DA ESTRUTURAÇÃO DOS ATIVOS NA TOMADA DE DECISÃO SOBRE INVESTIMENTOS NO SETOR DA ÁGUA. <i>JAIME GABRIEL SILVA</i>
20.00	GALA DINNER KAIS RESTAURANTE

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09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION ID 113. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS.
	Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez David Mckewon. Vicepresidente honorario del Instituto de Gestión de Activos Joe Amadi Echendu. Presidente de la Junta Directiva de la Sociedad Internacional de Gestión de Activos de Ingeniería Edmea Adell. Presidente de IFRAMI y miembro de ISO/TC 251 Asset Management Alan Wilson. Representante del Comité de Gestión de Activos de la Federación Europea de Sociedades Nacionales de Mantenimiento
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION. ID 135. THE ROLE OF ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE RESILIENCE OF CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE. EPAL
	Chair: Ana Margarida Luís. AdP Valor Miguel Freitas. E-REDES Vanessa Martins. EPAL Javier Serra. ENAGÁS Infraestructuras de Portugal
09.45 AUDITORIUM III	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION. CHAIR EDUARDO LEITE
ID 8	EUROPEAN ACTION TOWARDS MORE ENTREPRENEURIAL AND INNOVATIVE UNIVERSITIES. <i>NUNO ALMEIDA</i>
ID 74	ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: FAILURE PREVENTION AS A PILLAR FOR SUCESS. <i>EDUARDO LEITE</i>
ID 20	NETOBRA. A TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT FOR URBAN RESILIENCE IN THE AECO SECTOR. <i>SEYED REZVANI</i>
ID 117	SPOTLITE. RISK MONITORING FROM SPACE. <i>NUNO DURO</i>
ID 127	DIPROTOS. SISTEMA DE MONITORIZAÇÃO E VIGILÂNCIA DOS ATIVOS: PARQUES PÚBLICOS INFANTIS E DE LAZER. <i>ANTÓNIO ROQUE</i>
ID 94	BCIRCLE. PROJECTO "BOTICHAR". UMA UNIDADE DE PRODUÇÃO EFICIENTE E ESCALÁVEL. <i>DIEGO ARÁN</i>
ID 102	AECYCLE. SUSTAINABLE AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 109	CASADOMO. HABITAÇÃO INOVADORA E SUSTENTÁVEL EM SUPERDOBE MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS DA CIDADE DA PRAIA - CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTÉS</i>
09.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 2. CHAIR ANA LUÍSA CABRITA
ID 114	SUSTAINABILITY AND OTHER OUTCOMES - THE VALUE OF A STRATEGIC ASSET MANAGEMENT APPROACH. <i>DAVID MCKEOWN</i>

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ID 31	A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN EUROPE TO MEASURE THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT POLICIES, INDUSTRY ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY. <i>KHULOUD KALTHOUM</i>
ID 17	PROTECTING AND REALIZING VALUE FROM POLLINATION ASSETS: BEEKEEPING OR ASSET MANAGEMENT APPLIED TO NATURAL ASSETS?. <i>AZUCENA MARQUES</i>
ID 52	CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN INDUSTRY 5.0 – A RESEARCH AGENDA
ID 54	A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION AND AWARENESS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES BY MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN SANGO-OTA REGION, OGUN STATE NIGERIA. <i>ISRAEL DUNMADE</i>
ID 107	HARNESSING THE POWER OF BIOMIMICRY FOR SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION IN PRODUCT DESIGN AND INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT. <i>ARUNA M</i>
09.45 ROOM 5	RISK & RELIABILITY. CHAIR ANTONIO SÁNCHEZ.
ID 6	DATA MODEL TO DIGITIZATION OF CRITICALITY ANALYSIS IN RAILWAY SYSTEMS. <i>ÁNGEL MENA</i>
ID 1	APLICACIÓN DEL MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO (MGM) ALINEADO A UN PROCESO INTEGRAL DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS.CASO DE ESTUDIO: SINEA PERÚ, EMPRESA LÍDER EN LATINOAMÉRICA DEL SECTOR DE PRODUCCIÓN ENVASES RECICLADOS PARA BEBIDAS COMERCIALES (PET). <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 7	MATRIZ DE CRITICIDAD CUALITATIVA DE RIESGO (MCCR) APLICADA EN UNA LÍNEA DE PRODUCCIÓN DE ENVASES BIODEGRADABLES, <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 30	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VISÃO GERAL DA ESTRUTURA E FUNCIONAMENTO. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
ID 25	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VALIDAÇÃO COM BASE EM DADOS REAIS. <i>JOÃO VINAGRE AMADO</i>
11.15	COFFEE BREAK
11.45 AUDITORIUM I	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION. ID 125. INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT : PEOPLE , PROCESSES AND TECHNOLOGY AS ENABLERS FOR ISO 55001 CERTIFICATION. EVORA/SAP
	<i>Chair: Patrícia Franganito (Bureau Veritas) Tiago Fernandes (SAP EMEA) João Moura (Ernst & Young) Paula Branco (Metro do Porto) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>

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11.45 AUDITORIUM III	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 3. CHAIR HUGO PATRÍCIO.
ID 37	GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIER-BASED APPROACH ON WASTEWATER NETWORK AGE PREDICTION FOR CRITICAL ASSETS IDENTIFICATION. <i>RICARDO FERREIRA</i>
ID 49	DIGITALIZAÇÃO E ANÁLISE FUNCIONAL INTEGRADA (AFI) NO PROCESSO DE TOMADA DE DECISÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>HUGO BRANQUINHO</i>
ID 50	INFODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE DETECTION OF BRIDGES. <i>JORGE ALEXANDRE VIEIRA</i>
ID 57	MONITOREO DE LA SALUD ESTRUCTURAL MEDIANTE REALIDAD AUMENTADA Y VIRTUAL: UNA REVISIÓN INTEGRAL. <i>MATÍAS VALENZUELA</i>
ID 66	AVALIAÇÃO METODOLÓGICA DA APLICABILIDADE DA MONITORIZAÇÃO POR SATÉLITE NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS RODOFERROVIÁRIOS. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
11.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 3. CHAIR JOSÉ CAMPOS E MATOS.
ID 32	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS DE ÁGUAS PLUVIAIS EM MEIO URBANO EM PORTUGAL – DESAFIOS PARA O SETOR. <i>RITA SALGADO BRITO</i>
ID 39	REALITY CAPTURE AND MODELLING FOR DIGITAL WATER MANAGEMENT: CASE STUDY OF WATER INFRASTRUCTURE ASSETS IN BRAZIL. <i>WAGNER CARVALHO</i>
ID 81	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA AVALIAÇÃO DA QUALIDADE NA GESTÃO E OTIMIZAÇÃO DE ATIVOS FOTOVOLTAICOS. <i>TERESA CANELAS</i>
ID 93	PATHWAYS TOWARDS NET-ZERO: MARKET DATA INSIGHTS ON PORTUGUESE REAL ESTATE ENERGY PERFORMANCE
ID 100	TRANSIÇÃO DIGITAL E INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA NO SETOR AECO - ESTRATÉGIAS INTEGRADAS PARA UM FUTURO SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 105	COMO TORNAR UM AMS – ASSET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OPERACIONAL E SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>EDMEA ADELL</i>
11.45 ROOM 5	PEOPLE AND COMPETENCE. CHAIR TICO MONTEIRO
ID 10	INNOVATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT SKILLS TOWARDS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO SILVA</i>
ID 53	PROFICIÊNCIA DIGITAL DE ESTUDANTES DE ENGENHARIA: DESAFIOS E OPORTUNIDADES NO CENÁRIO EUROPEU. <i>CELIA DO CARMO LEANDRO</i>

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ID 60	FORTALECENDO A RESILIÊNCIA CLIMÁTICA EM SÃO TOMÉ E PRÍNCIPE: CAPACITAÇÃO DE JORNALISTAS PARA UMA COMUNICAÇÃO EFICAZ.
ID 87	PROPUESTA DE METODOLOGÍA DE GESTIÓN DEL CAMBIO COMO COMPLEMENTO AL MARCO DE REFERENCIA PARA UNA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS INTANGIBLES Y CONOCIMIENTO. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA
ID 118	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA FORMAÇÃO PARA UM MELHOR DESEMPENHO NOS MÉTODOS E PLANEAMENTO DA MANUTENÇÃO DE ATIVOS. DÉRCIO DIAS
ID 2	CRITICAL ASSETS AND VALUE NETWORKS IN RESILIENT INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN THE EU OUTERMOST REGIONS. EDUARDO LEITE
13.15 AUDITORIUM I	CLOSING CEREMONY BEST PAPER DIGITALIZATION BEST PAPER SUSTAINABILITY ENTERPREUNERSHIP COMPETITION LIFETIME ACHIEVEMENT AWARD
13.45	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
